

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

High Resolution Audio Analysis From A Music Information Retrieval Perspective

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Supervisor: Dr. Frederic Font Cabrera

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Dedication

To the sound community, hoping this document can support future studies or supply knowledge that can be useful in different working situations.

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Abstract

Since long time ago digital audio is one of the most used formats in the industry for storage and transmission. During the mayor part of its history, from a not audio professional, but a consumer perspective, 44.1 kHz/16 bits have been the standard resolution used for music final reproduction. As data storage became cheaper and sample rate converters more accurate and powerful, higher sampling resolutions start gaining importance within audio professionals, where all types of opinions and discussions have raised, about if it's worth it to work with higher resolutions. With the main objective to find if perceptual attributes can be mapped to High Resolution Audio (HRA), this thesis gathers information from latest studies about perceptual attributes classification within HRA, once all the information is covered, results from a listening experiment are presented. Raw data, obtained from the results of the experiment, show a small preference from part of the assessors to choose HRA over standard quality, but final statistical tests reject this hypothesis.

Keywords: High Resolution Audio; Digital Audio; Sampling Rate; Loudness; Streaming.

Chapter 1

Introduction

Audio digital sampling gives the opportunity to sound researchers and professionals, almost infinite amount of data to work with. It can be stored and carried easily from one system to another, which opens the possibility to replicate and test different hypotheses in order to generate useful knowledge for every working area within sound. This industry has grown fast during the last decades and as a result of, new studies and a variable number of specialization areas have emerged, where different communication protocols, and conversion standards are set in order to improve or maintain the quality of the information transmitted.

One important thing that should be taken in consideration when studying about "*Audio quality*", is that the term "*quality*", must be not measured as a total, because degradation can be occurring at different stages of an electro-acoustic chain simultaneously, or every particular task permits different thresholds, given so, it has to be studied at specific places of the transmission chain. Interoperability issues can drive to audio degradation, which implies losing resolution; sampling resolution has been mapped by industry to audio quality, in terms that HIGH RESOLUTION AUDIO (HRA) is supposed to have higher quality than standard CD resolution, or when comparing the top state of the arts professional recording gear with amateur audio chains with cheaper components and less accurate circuits designs.

Proper practices are already well identified by professionals, these are required in or-

der to preserve homogeneity, in terms of obtaining the most accurate representation of the signal that is being recorded and after all the analog or digital processing, but high resolution audio still is a trending topic that continuously generates divided discussions, giving so, this research replicates a daily working situation for most recording engineers, in order to retrieve data, information and knowledge, that hopefully can be applied in the HRA research field.

1.1 Motivation

Numerous important studies have been done, in order to identify if it's possible for humans to discriminate between different sampling resolutions and quantizations. One of the latest and most relevant researches within this area, was a meta-analysis made by Dr. Joshua Reiss [1], he presents a significant statistical difference in sampling rate perception, where he observed that trained subjects obtain better results when compared to subjects without any experience in audio, at the time of choosing from multiple samples the one with higher resolution.

Quantization was left as an unstudied topic, but after several studies, [2] points that during their experiments, subjects didn't show any discrimination capacities between 16 bits and 24 bits, suggesting that HRA benefits more from a wider frequency range than the bit depth.

Taking in consideration already well known musical information retrieval attributes and supported by perceptual experiments, this research main motivation is to generate useful knowledge, that contributes to the previously mentioned studies and audio producers who work with HRA, and gather relevant data that can be used for future research works.

1.2 Objectives

If well trained professionals can discriminate between low and high resolution audio, this can imply that somehow HRA have psychoacoustic effects on them. Through perceptual experiments try to propose some possible explanation about this phenomena, and if there are relevant results map them to sound classification attributes [3]. Finally release the information so it can be used in further studies, or as HRA meta-data in audio streaming services or platforms such as [Freesound.org](https://www.freesound.org) [4].

Chapter 2

State of the Arts

This chapter covers and introduces digital audio, high resolution audio contents and standards, modern day HRA technologies and latest researches within audio quality perception matter.

2.1 Physics of Sound

2.1.1 Sound Signals

Sound is produced by vibrating objects that cause a disturbance in a medium; for humans, air is their surrounding medium; these vibrations displace the air molecules that are next to it, and these molecules the molecules that are next to them, and so on, occasioning changes in air pressure. The moment when the vibrating object reaches its maximum displacement the molecules of air next to it will be closer together, this effect is called *Compression*, as it can be observed in figure 1. Since there is a restoring force that pulls the object to move back to its original position, this will cause the object to displace in the opposite direction, causing a drop in air pressure, provoking the molecules disturb farther apart, known as *Refraction*. The maximum is the displacement the maximum the amplitude of the sound wave.

¹Image source: http://www.midichords.com/ckeditor_assets/pictures/56/content_noise-2.png

Figure 1: Sound transmitted through the air from a source to a human ear.¹

When changes in pressure follow a repetitive pattern, it is said that the sound has a *periodic waveform*, in contrast, noise is *aperiodic* where there is not a detectable pattern [5], in between these two extremes there is an endless domain of variations.

A *cycle* is one repetition of a periodic waveform, just by measuring how many cycles are in one second, it's possible to know the fundamental frequency of a waveform, where *Hertz (Hz)* (H. Hertz 1930) is used as its unit of measure. The length of the cycle can be expressed as *wavelength (λ)*, determining that the greater the wavelength the lower the frequency and vice versa.

The most simple periodic signal is called *sine wave*, named because it can be obtained by calculating the sine of an angle.

$$y(t) = A \sin(2\pi f t + \theta)$$

Fourier theorem states that complex periodic signals are composed of a harmonic series of sine waves, the fundamental frequency and a number of frequencies multiples of this fundamental, called *Harmonics*. For example a complex periodic signal with a fundamental frequency of 100 Hz, will have as its multiples harmonics 200, 300, 400, 500 Hz and so on as observed in figure 2.

Figure 2: Complex Periodic Signal

The amplitude and phase relationship between these sine waves determine the unique timbre of a source. Pohlmann [6] emphasizes that harmonic structures explain why humans have limitations when distinguishing the timbre of high frequency sources, the first harmonic of a 10 kHz fundamental frequency will be 20 kHz, which is mainly out of the human hearing range. This leaves an open discussion for later in this document about why higher sample rates will determine high resolution, although some say it is not needed because the frequencies it can sample exceed our physical capabilities.

2.1.2 Phase

Considering the two dimensional plot shown in figure 3, the *initial phase* of a waveform is determined by where its starting point is located in the Y axis, the cosine function of the wave.

Figure 3: Phase cycle.²

²Image source: <http://www.electronics-tutorials.ws/accircuits/phasors.html>

When two correlated signals arrive at the same time and (*angle*) with respect to the *Y* axis, at a specific measurement point, they are said to be *phase aligned*.

Figure 4: Two signals in phase.

When one of the signals is time delayed or its polarity is inverted respect to the other, they will be *out of phase*. The phase is a major variable to take in account when talking about audio quality because two main factors:

a) *Phase Distortion*

Every digital signal processing chain will add some time delay to the signal, so when summing the original signal with the processed one, to obtain a new signal, an audibly phase shift may occur which can affect the stereo imaging or produce a kind of phasing or flanging effect.

b) *Cancellation*

If the phase shift is among a range of approximately $\pi/2$ and $3\pi/2$ of the fundamental frequency, the signal at that specific frequency and it's multiples can lose important information or even be canceled at all.

Figure 5: Two Signals out of phase.

2.2 Digital Audio

2.2.1 Digital Representation

From different theoretical sources we can deduce that under strict conditions any continuous analog signal can be converted into a discrete time signal. One of the core terms of digital audio is *sampling*, which consists on foot printing the pattern of a waveform with a series of samples over time, samples are no more than just binary values which store the amplitude of the analog signal. This is called *pulse-code-modulation*, first patented by the British researcher A. Reeves (Reeves 1983).

2.2.2 Analog to digital conversion

Process when *continuous-time* signals are converted to *discrete-time* signals. Electric signals, for example air pressure changes captured by a microphone or an instrument signal, are sent through an ADC (Analog-to-Digital Converter), this device is in charge of converting at a periodical *time sampling*, given by a master clock,

the changes in voltage into binary numbers as amplitude values in time, *amplitude quantization*. The binary numbers are saved in a digital memory.

2.2.3 Discrete Time Sampling

The digital signal is created by taking samples every certain periodic time, every gray vertical bar observed in figure 6 are these samples. The *sampling period* or *sampling frequency*, rate how many samples per second are taken, using Hertz (Hz) as its unit of measure. Sampling can be a lossless process if the input signal is properly preprocessed. There are many sampling theorems that recommend the ideal sampling rate for many different disciplines, but in digital audio, specially for music recording and reproduction, the most recognized ones are the *Nyquist Theorem* (H. Nyquist 1925), who wasn't the first to propose a sampling theorem, but the first to clarify its application to communications, and the *Shannon Theorem* (C. Shannon 1937), where he proved that circuits can solve logical problems using Boolean Algebra.

Figure 6: Comparison between different sample rates and bit depths³

Both Nyquist and Shannon theorems state that a continuous signal with frequency content from 0 to $N/2$ can be represented by a discrete signal with a sampling rate of N , which doubles the highest frequency that want to be sampled. As discussed before the sampling process is based on a time unit, i.e., lower frequencies will have more samples per period than higher frequencies as shown in 7; for short periods, those

³Image source: http://www.realhd-audio.com/wp-content/uploads/2014/05/140514_bit_length_sr_comp_avs.jpg

present in frequencies that are near the limits of the humans listening capabilities, two samples are enough to represent a signal.

Figure 7: Number of samples depend on the frequency period⁴

It is important to have in mind the theorems' norm about limiting the input signal to no more than the half of the sampling frequency, this can be achieved using low pass anti-aliasing filters. Filters cannot attenuate the signal strictly at the Nyquist frequency, that's why usually the highest frequency to be sampled is some thousand frequencies above in order to have a safe band for the filter to act, and attenuate the frequencies that can create aliasing distortion. Aliasing is a sampling error when there are not enough samples to represent information above the Nyquist Frequency, a fold down perceptual effect occurs, adding to the sampled signal new frequencies that were not present in the input signal.

2.2.4 Quantization

The range of values, for each sample that is taken, must be sufficiently large enough to represent in the most accurate way the amplitude of the signal at that specific time. The range depends on the number of bits designated to store these values, one bit can only have two values 1 or 0, so the higher number of bits the higher possibilities to store different values. Number of values increases by the power of two (e.g., from 16 bits we have $2^{16} = 65,536$ possible values). Samples are usually

⁴Image source: CreatedwithSinetonegeneratoratAudacity

represented as an integer, so if the value of a signal is between two integers, let's say 50 and 51, the converter might round it to one of the two nearest integers, differing slightly from the original signal. This problem is known as quantization error or quantization noise because it can be perceived as white noise.

Dither is used to mitigate the effects of quantization error, and is a more efficient and less expensive technique than increasing the number of bits. It is a small amount of noise, uncorrelated with the signal, which causes a shift into the audio signal with respect of the quantization values, making each quantization cycle different from each other, randomizing its effects to the point of elimination.

2.2.5 Digital to analog conversion

D/A converter accepts a coded binary signal, and reconstructs with it an analog waveform. It also has to minimize any prejudicial effects of data storage, and timing errors. Phase-locked loops and data buffer, are one of the most important tasks performed by the reproduction circuits. A buffer is a memory that receives data irregularly, but it is controlled by the master clock in order to stream this data at the same rate that it was took.

No matter which coding technique was used in order to obtain the modulated audio data, it is commonly demodulated to non-return to zero code (NRZ), which is a simple code in where amplitude level represents the binary information, leaving ready the data for further reproduction processing. At the error correction circuit data is arranged in a bit stream to secure that any deficiency does not affect successive data, checking for errors that may have occurred following the encoding. Demultiplexer circuit accepts the bit stream, acts as a buffer, and when all the information, of a complete word, has been received it outputs all the bits simultaneously, in a parallel form, leaving it ready for the digital to analog conversion. A D/A converter accepts the data and converts it to an output analog voltage or current. As an example of how a D/A converter works, the weighted-resistor D/A, one of the simplest kinds of converters, bits are assigned to a series of resistors and switches, where a reference voltage generates a current through the resistors, and binary values are in charge of

closing "1" and opening "0" the switches. Finally an operational amplifier sums the currents and converts them to an output voltage.

2.3 High Resolution Audio Contents and Standards

High Resolution Audio, known as (HRA) main intention is to provide great sound clarity and a detailed representation about the recorded source and location, or how it was listened in a controlled space like a post-production studio, the way the creators intended. The Audio Division of the Consumer Technology Association (CTA), developed a guide which is intended to review HRA practices and standards, to follow in order to preserve the minimum quality needed to comply as HRA. The *CTA* and *The Recording Academy* describe Hi-Res Audio as "lossless audio that is capable of reproducing the full range of sound from recordings that have been mastered from better than CD quality music sources".

It has passed several years from now, when it was first proposed the necessity to work with a digital quality that was able to exceed the quality present back then in the analog tapes, where for example a 30 ips half inch analog tape was able to go beyond 40 kHz, and the residual noise of the high performance analog equipment was more than 120 dBs below it's maximum output level. [7]

2.3.1 Digital Loudness

Loudness can be described as the human perception of "volume", and audio quality has been suffering, during the last decades, because the loudness war. The industry has been competing about how to sound louder than their competition, and as result distorted productions with less dynamic range, which give a less pleasurable experience for listeners.

Modern day streaming or broadcast services, follow some series of standards in order to obtain an equilibrated reproduction, in terms of "volume" when changing from file to file, modifying the original levels of the files that doesn't fit their needs, this process is commonly called "*Playback Loudness Reference Level*", "*Loudness*

Management" or "Normalization". Figure 8 shows how this process can affect any audio file.

Online music services manage loudness. Each has a different "target" replay loudness level. Loud songs are turned down, quieter songs may be turned up - and that's where things get interesting

www.productionadvice.co.uk/online-loudness

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Figure 8: Streaming Normalization⁵

⁵Image source: <http://productionadvice.co.uk/online-loudness/>

- Up grade

When a file level is under the Target Loudness, the streaming service will raise it level, to the desired level. The file will even play louder than the original file, without any extra modification.

- Down grade

If the file average levels are over the Target Loudness, the automatic processing of the streaming service will lower the levels, in order to take the signal down the threshold. Taking into account that the process is applied over already mastered files, this causes the file to loose presence, perceptually speaking, and it will sound even weaker than a file that comply since the beginning with the Target Loudness.

2.3.2 Hardware

Figure 9: Hi-Res Audio Logo

Most sound professionals main goal when operating an audio system is to obtain a homogeneous signal all through the electro-acoustic chain, with the minimum latency possible and degradation. As different are the specializations within sound, different are the variables to be considered in order to obtain correlation between the input and the output signals. Sound distortions, noise (sync, induction, etc.) and package loss are mainly the most common issues present. When thinking digital, figure 10 represents in a good way to how the signal can be affected by different sampling rates.

⁶Image source: <http://samplerateconverter.com/content/how-improve-sound-quality>

Figure 10: Harmonic distortion comparison between different sampling formats.⁶

2.3.3 Audio Content

Figure 11: Hi-Res Music Logo

Based on the HRA description proposed by the The CTA and The Recording Academy, in order for an audio file to be considered as HRA it has to be in a *Lossless Audio Formats*. Since this field starts gaining importance, many sampling rates and techniques have evolved, covering the necessity of a digital representation that can be compared to analog tape capabilities; in terms of this research will be considered any format that goes beyond 88.2 kHz.

- **Direct Stream Digital (DSD)**

Direct recording and transfer of modulated 1bit signal.

Sampling frequency 11.2 MHz (256*44.1 kHz).

Frequency Response: Flat to 100 kHz.

Instead of using PCM method, it uses PDM (Pulse Density Modulation).

⁷<http://www.merging.com/products/pyramix/dsd-dxd>

Figure 12: DSD: One of the formats with highest sampling rate.⁷

- **Digital Extreme Definition (DXD)**

352.8 kHz - 24 bits.

It was created to seamlessly convert from PDM (DSD Format) to PCM.

Developed by Mergin Technologies.

- **Dolby True HD**

Eight full-range channels of 96 kHz/24-bit audio.

Six full-range channels of 192 kHz/24-bit audio.

Advance 96 kHz up-sampling mode from 48kHz.

3D object based upgrade compatibility.

- **DTS HD Master Audio**

Eight full-range channels of 96 kHz/24-bit audio.

Six full-range channels of 192 kHz/24-bit audio.

3D object based upgrade compatibility.

- **MQA**

"Origami" folding hierarchical technology.

Up to 768 kHz internal decoding.

Need of a dedicated renderer.

2.3.4 Streaming and Download Services

Fiber optic Internet access opened the possibilities of working with more bandwidth and stream higher data content. Services that work with HRA have started showing up, most of them offer all types of resolutions, where some special configurations or searches, are needed in order to access the higher resolution archives. Some of the most relevant are listed below:

- TIDAL
- Deezer Elite
- Qobuz
- HD Tracks
- 7 Digital

Streamed audio is still far to achieve the quality obtained from downloaded files or the physical formats. Figure 13 show a comparison between different streaming services, where can be observed that TIDAL is the one with the highest bit rate now a days.

Streaming services compared

	Spotify	Apple Music	Amazon Music Unlimited	Tidal	Google Play Music
Monthly fee	\$9.99, £9.99, AU\$11.99	\$9.99, £9.99, AU\$11.99	\$7.99 for Amazon Prime members, \$9.99 for non-Prime members, \$3.99 for Echo-only service	Premium: \$9.99, £9.99, AU\$14.99; HiFi: \$19.99, £19.99, AU\$23.99	\$9.99, £9.99, AU\$11.99
Free option?	Yes, with ads	No	No	No	Yes
Free trial period	30 days	3 months	30 days	30 days	30 days
Advertised music library size	More than 30 million	30 million	"tens of millions"	25 million	30 million
Maximum bitrate	320Kbps	256Kbps	256Kbps	1,411Kbps	320Kbps

Figure 13: Tidal Bit Rate.⁸

2.4 Audio Quality Research

2.4.1 Auditory Perception Studies

For designing experiments that measure perceived quality, there are two well-known methods recommended by the International Telecommunication Union (ITU).

a) **The ITU-R BS.1116** [8], is presented as: *"intended for use in the assessment of systems which introduce impairments so small as to be undetectable without rigorous control of the experimental conditions and appropriate statistical analysis."*

b) **The ITU-R BS.1534-3** [9], know as the MUSHRA method is suitable for evaluation of intermediate audio quality. It is mainly used for lower quality situations, such as the quality obtain from streaming services.

Both of the studies are based on the Basic Audio Quality (BAQ) parameter. It's a global attribute used to judge any detected differences between a reference signal and the result of it after being processed, where for some attributes are used for listening test evaluations.

⁸Image source: <https://www.cnet.com/how-to/best-music-streaming-service/>

2.4.2 Meta-Analysis of previous relevant researches

An important attribution was made by Dr. Joshua Reiss [1]. Reiss meta-analysis was focused on discrimination studies concerning high resolution audio. The research embraced 18 of the most relevant audio quality perception studies, and data from more than 400 participants in over 12,500 trials. He found a statistically significant ability to discriminate between standard CD or video standard resolution and HRA. Trained listeners results were far significant than those without any experience in audio or music; this support what MUSHRA method [9] proposes, that by the time of working with subjects on an experiment, these ones should have relevant training and experience within the area of study.

2.4.3 Attributes Categorization

A similar study was made in order to obtain the most relevant attributes mapped from different research works. Subjects and researchers used attributes to categorize audio stimulus [3]. From a large list of words, they cluster them in four major categories:

Table 1: **SPACE**

Reverberation	Spatial Distribution	Localization
Spatialization	Immersion	Envelopment
Distance	Width	Depth

Lately used mainly to evaluate surround sound systems

Table 2: **DEFECTS**

Disruption	Hiss	Distortion	Background Noise	Hum
------------	------	------------	------------------	-----

Table 3: **QUALITY**

Dynamics	Stability	Homogeneity	Fidelity	Realism
----------	-----------	-------------	----------	---------

Table 4: **TIMBER QUALITY**

Richness	Clarity	Hardness
Brightness	Tone Color	Coloration
	Equalization	

Reducing the number of attributes into shorter lists, can provide a better understanding at the time of running discrimination tests, which can result in a more accurate result, and less time expended during the trials.

Chapter 3

Methods

This chapter describes the main considerations followed during the experiments, in order to obtain the desired data. AS first, all the electro-acoustic chains are described and explained, supported by signal flow diagrams and relevant specifications of the hardware and software are mentioned, finishing with a detailed explanation of how listening experiments were performed with subjects, and the final data gathered.

3.1 Materials

One continuous signal, was divided in three, and then routed to different recording gear from different brands.¹ Figure 14 shows how the signal was split using a Yamaha analog mixer, and then recorded by three different setups. Although the main goal was not to find any differences between the performance of each specific brand, but working with different electronic components give the opportunity to gather data from different timbers and qualities, that can then be used for multiple purposes.

¹Splitting is optional because with just one digital representation the experiment can be done.

Figure 14: Recording electro-acoustic chain

3.1.1 Hardware Specifications

Table 5: **RME OCTAMIC XTC**

SNR AD	113 dB RMS unweighted, 117 dBA
THD	< 0.0003%, < -110dB
Frequency response	@ 192 kHz, -1 dB: 8 Hz - 94 kHz
SNR DA	@ 115 dB RMS unweighted, 118 dBA
Frequency response	@ 192 kHz, -1 dB: 8 Hz - 75 kHz

Table 6: **AVID HD OMNI**

SNR AD	Not Specified
THD	0,00045 %, -107 dB
Frequency response (Mic Pres)	20 Hz to 20 kHz (\approx 0,05 dB)
SNR DA	Not Specified
Frequency response	Not Specified

Table 7: **Roland UA-101**

SNR AD	101 dB
THD	Not Specified
Frequency response	@ 96.0 kHz: 20 Hz to 40 kHz (+1/-1 dB)
SNR DA	107 dB

Internal 192 kHz AD/DA conversion

The listening tests were performed directly from the DA converter. A stereo monitor headphones output from a *RME HDSPe MADI FX PCIe* was used to do the D/A conversion at a sampling rate of 192 kHz. The resultant signal was reproduced through a pair of headphones *Beyerdynamic DT 990 Pro*.

Table 8: **HDSPe MADI FX**

Signal-to-Noise (DR)	110 dB RMS unweighted, 113 dBA @ 44.1 kHz
Channel separation	> 100 dB
Output	6.3 mm TRS
Output impedance	75 Ω
Output level at 0 dBFS	@ +13 dBu

Table 9: **Beyerdynamic DT 990 Pro**

Nominal frequency response	5 - 35,000 Hz unweighted, 113 dBA @ 44.1 kHz
Nominal impedance	250 Ω per cartridge
Nominal SPL	96 dB SPL
Nominal T.H.D	< 0.2%

Figure 15: Frequency Response Headphones²

3.1.2 Ableton Live Process

Ableton Live has shown to be one of the most used and powerful softwares for electronic music composition and sampling purposes. It has a special interface and functionality for working with clips which opened the possibility to record simultaneously clips from the three different signals and left them ready in the same session, in order to be used for the listening experiments. Figure 16 gives a better impression on how the recording process was made.

Figure 16: Ableton Live Recording session³

²Image source: <http://europe.beyerdynamic.com/shop/hah/headphones-and-headsets/studio-and-stage/studio-headphones/dt-990-pro.html>

Clips were arranged by different sampling resolutions at different channels (colors), and the different recordings in descending order. Each sample was trimmed, named and annotated depending on its type and desired length. Once all the editing was done, with the option "*Crop Clips*", the clips were saved with all the changes done, without changing sampling rates. When doing this process at Ableton Live, the samples are saved to the *./Samples/Processed* inside the project root carpet.

3.2 Experiment Assessors

Based on recommendations proposed by the studies mentioned before in the States of the Arts, the group should consist of well trained and experienced musicians or engineers that somehow work with sound and music. It had been shown that people with this kind of skills, are able to discriminate between standard CD resolution and HRA. The higher the quality reached by the systems to be tested, the more important it is to have experienced listeners. [9]

The MUSHRA method recommends that no more than 20 assessors is sufficient for drawing appropriate conclusions. If rigorous experimental control cannot be achieved, then larger numbers of assessors might be needed to attain useful data.

For this project, it was possible to run the experiment with fifteen assessors. No matter that all the assessors were involved in sound related working areas, but from the total amount of listeners just five participants were considered as experts, because of their years of experience in the industry or because their working field somehow involve high resolution audio.

3.3 Experiment Procedure

3.3.1 Samples Rates Converters Synchronization

During the experiment samples were reproduced at the maximum sampling rate the hardware was able to work at, 192 kHz/24 bits. Listeners had to do several discrimination tasks between samples that were recorded at 44.1 kHz and a 192

kHz, both quantized at 24 bits.

3.3.2 Loudness Control

To avoid any possible bias because of level differences, and JND perception issues, an equal loudness process was applied to the samples that were used for listening discrimination. First the tool r128x⁴ was used to easily check the loudness values of each clip 17.

The screenshot shows the r128x application window with a table of processing results. The table has five columns: Error, File Name, Program Loudness, Loudness Range, and dBTP. There are four rows of data, all with an error of 0.

Error	File Name	Program Loudness	Loudness Range	dBTP
0	A_MajorScales_Organni_192-24.wav	-15.3	2.1	-2.7
0	A_MajorScales_Organni_44-24.wav	-15.9	1.6	-3.4
0	C_SingleLowPitchNote_192-24.wav	-21.3	1.7	-6.5
0	C_SingleLowPitchNote_44-24.wav	-21.1	1.1	-6.7

Figure 17: Loudness Measured with r128x App

In order to have a second reference and adjust gain values, the Waves plug-in *WLM Plus Loudness Meter* was used⁵. The final values once adjusted are shown at figure 18, this values were selected in order to work within recommended loudness ranges of different streaming services.

A_MajorScales_Organni_192-24	A_MajorScales_Organni_44-24	-12 LUFS
C_SingleLowPitchNote_192-24	C_SingleLowPitchNote_44-24	-18 LUFS

Figure 18: Longterm Loudness Adjusted Values

3.3.3 Listening test

The subjects had to categorize, between two samples, the one they thought it was a the closest representation for each specific attribute: Loudness, Dynamic Range, Reverberation and Richness. Samples were arranged in a different order for every participant, without any color difference or specific marks, that could differentiate between each other. If sequences of audio were identical for all participants, it

⁴<https://github.com/audionuma/r128x>

⁵Useful tutorials can be found on Waves YouTube channel

would be difficult to know if there were influenced due to that sequence rather than to sampling rate differences.

ITU-R BS pointed that the duration of each sample should be approximately 10s. A modification of this rule is presented by Dr. Reiss [1], where the usage of samples longer than 20 seconds are recommended, in order to give listeners more time to really decode the information; for this reason the duration of each sample available at the dataset used was about 26 seconds.

If discrimination ⁶ results showed that at least 50% of the runs, participants choose the samples with highest resolution, a second run was performed in order to measure reliability. ⁷

Training assessors

A reference channel, with example clips, was added to the test GUI. Reference signals help the listener to train their hearing in order to be aware of what to listen at the time of a discrimination task. Two different samples were presented for each attribute, one that represented in great measure the attribute they were going to work with, and one that is far from being similar. Figure 19 show how the session was arranged.

Figure 19: Ableton Live Recording and listening session⁸

⁶Discrimination: A measure of the ability to perceive differences between test items.

⁷Reliability: A measure of the closeness of repeated ratings of the same test item.

Chapter 4

Results

This chapter presents the data gathered from the discrimination tests. It was obtained following the procedures explained during the methodology in this document.

Data visualization presents the raw data, where it can be observed at first instance, a small significant difference where participants tend to choose 192 kHz over 44 kHz. In order to have a clearer idea about the results, a hypothesis test was performed.

ISO or ITU standards for audio quality measurements were followed as close as possible, but still some standards were missing because of space limitations, hardware available, and not all subjects were audio experts. The experiment was based on obtaining categorical data, leaving an open discussion that can deepen through new research works with more robust experiments and controlled conditions.

4.1 Preliminary Results

4.1.1 Data Visualization

The data presented was normalized in a range from 0 to 1. The correct discriminations, in this case the instances where listeners choose 192 kHz over 44.1 kHz, a "1" was assigned, and to the incorrect ones a "0", meaning participants choose 44 kHz.

The first figure 20 shows a comparison using the results from all the assessors. Blue

colors are the correct instances, i.e., 192 kHz, and the red ones for the occasions where 44.1 kHz was chosen.

Figure 20: Comparison between percentages from all assessors

In the reliability run, assessors with less than 0.5% correct choices, were not taken into account. The second figure 21, represent the values of just the participants that were able to correctly discriminate at least 50% of the runs.

Figure 21: Data from assessors > 0.5

4.2 Hypothesis Test

With the raw data was not easy to find a clear result. In order to show a significant explanation, either to reject or accept the null hypothesis of this work, the Chi-Square Test for Categorical Data was performed, establishing $\alpha = 0.05$

Chi-Square theory suggests that as the first step to test the hypothesis, is necessary to check if expected frequencies values are greater or equal to five " $e_{ij} \geq 5$ ". The values of the first calculations can be observed at figure 22.

alpha	0.05				
Observed Frequencies					
Row Labels	Dynamics	Loudnees	Reverb	Richness	Grand Total
44	7	5	9	7	28
192	11	13	9	11	44
Grand Total	18	18	18	18	72
Sample Proportions					
Row Labels	Dynamics	Loudnees	Reverb	Richness	Grand Total
44	38.89%	27.78%	50.00%	38.89%	38.89%
192	61.11%	72.22%	50.00%	61.11%	61.11%
Grand Total	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%
Sample Proportions					
Row Labels	Dynamics	Loudnees	Reverb	Richness	Grand Total
44	7.0	7.0	7.0	7.0	28.0
192	11.0	11.0	11.0	11.0	44.0
Grand Total	18.0	18.0	18.0	18.0	72.0
Expected Frequencies					
Row Labels	Dynamics	Loudnees	Reverb	Richness	Overall Proportions
44	7.00000	7.00000	7.00000	7.00000	0.388888889
192	11.00000	11.00000	11.00000	11.00000	0.611111111
Grand Total	18.00000	18.00000	18.00000	18.00000	1.00000

Figure 22: First steps of the test

Because all the values of the expected frequencies are greater than five, is possible to continue in order to obtain the *p-value*, which, when compared to alpha, if its value is lower, the null hypothesis can be accepted.

From observations at the preliminary results, and the final p-value calculation, presented at the figure 23, there's no clear evidence that different sampling rates, have

Deviation Square				
Sample Rates	Dynamics	Loudnees	Reverb	Richness
44	0.00000	4.00000	4.00000	0.00000
192	0.00000	4.00000	4.00000	0.00000

Deviation Squared/ Expected Freqs				
Sample Rates	Dynamics	Loudnees	Reverb	Richness
44	0.00000	0.57143	0.57143	0.00000
192	0.00000	0.36364	0.36364	0.00000

Test-Statistics Chi-Square = $\chi^2 =$	1.87013
k - count populations -	4
df	3
p-value	0.599794063
chi-critical value	7.814727903

Figure 23: p-value final results

different perceptual effects based on the attributes selected for this experiment; the short number of specialized assessors, as well as the limited possibilities to perform the experiment under a strict controlled situation, may be one of the possible reason of the high result of the *p-value*.

Chapter 5

Discussions and Conclusions

5.1 Data Discussion

With the amount of data gathered, it's not easy to have a clear point of view and reliable results. At first instance, from the graphics 21 it's possible to observe, from just the raw calculation of means, interesting behaviors and a small preference for 192 kHz on most of the attributes. The total means from the selections of 192 kHz over 44 kHz, is greater at almost all attributes, except Reverb, that is even for both sampling rates.

Attributes related to volume perception, at the first round of the experiment present a high discrimination value, although for the reliability runs, their values decreases in a considerable amount. It can be possible that after doing a first run of experiments, assessors listening can get tired or distracted, reducing the loudness or changes in dynamic perception.

The most contradictory result can be observed for the Reverb attribute, the first run a sustained low pitch note was presented to the assessors, and for the reliability runs a high pitched one. Results somehow show that maybe Reverb can be confused with high frequency content, which somehow a similar behavior on Richness reflects this.

Although means as a first overall observation expose positive results, the *p-value* is over the α *value*, rejecting any possibility to prove the null hypothesis, and map high resolution audio perception with the attributes selected.

5.1.1 Feature Work

If trained people tend to choose the samples with higher sampling rate, it could mean that there is a greater correlation between the perceptual attributes, especially the ones that measure loudness or dynamics, and more dense digital representations (more samples). Having in mind the measurements provided by Merging Technologies, where they show that the higher is the sampling rate, the closer the digital representation is to a continuous signal, this could lead to start a research work about sampling density and its psychoacoustic effects. If there are relevant results, using different tools as the ones proposed in the Audio Commons Initiative [10], through feature extraction and machine learning classification tasks, HRA streaming services can benefit in order to stream higher resolution content, discriminating audio quality if there are several samples of one same sound, and also get advantage to sound better and louder through the most used small reproduction systems.

5.2 Conclusions

Mastering engineers have been pointing that songs with more dynamic, have more impact on spectators, than the ones that are over compressed. Sampling density, although it has not been proven yet, may contribute in the process of preserving dynamic in actual sound productions. Working with higher sampling rates, not only gives the possibility to work at lower dBFS, but also of creating a perception of higher volume, which normal music consumers have perceived it as better quality.

Audio quality is a complex attribute to measure, even more nowadays where technology constantly becomes more precise for every different specific tasks and HRA is still an unexplored growing area, with short standardization norms. It's well known that just two samples are enough to digitally represent the highest frequency that we humans are able to hear, but latest studies are showing a significant statistical

correlation between audio quality perception and digital representations with higher sampling rates, but until now, included this study, it have been not possible to determine a clear reason of this phenomena. Is still an open question, to prove if denser sampled digital signals, which are closer representations of a continuous signal, affect in a great manner psycho-acoustically speaking, the loudness perception.

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